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SAFEGUARDING PRIVACY IN EDUCATIONAL DATA: ETHICAL CHALLENGES AND IMPLICATIONS OF ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE

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Applications of Artificial Intelligence (AI) are increasingly integrated into the field of modern education, both in-person and remote, as they enhance and enrich the educational experience. AI introduces a new, innovative model of teaching and learning that offers significant benefits to both students and educators. However, the potential risks associated with the use of AI in education must be investigated and assessed. A significant challenge in AI applications within education is the management and protection of educational-personal data. In this context, this article examines the need to protect the privacy of educational data collected through AI applications and explores the ethical dilemmas and concerns raised by their use, as well as the potential for unfair processing or data breaches.

Keywords: Artificial Intelligence, Privacy Protection, Educational - personal data

■ 1. Introduction

Applications of Artificial Intelligence (AI) are becoming increasingly integral to the field of contemporary education, both in-person and remote, as they enhance and enrich the learning experience. AI introduces a new, innovative model of teaching and learning that incorporates advanced digital tools and applications such as machine learning, deep learning, and educational analytics. These technologies en-

hance the teaching process and open new areas at all educational levels. Such developments offer significant benefits to both students and educators by fostering personalized learning, timely assessment, and self-directed education, while simultaneously saving time and improving the teaching process.

Artificial Intelligence (AI) applications can support students during exam preparation by providing personalized feedback and study plans. Chatbots and virtual teachers can assist students in engaging in interactive learning activities, while customized self-assessment exercises can identify areas where students need more attention. Furthermore, AI applications can contribute to ensuring the integrity of examinations by detecting plagiarism. Additionally, AI-operated monitoring systems can supervise students during exams and flag any suspicious behavior, thereby preventing cheating (Triantafyllakis, 2024).

However, the potential risks that could arise from the applications of Artificial Intelligence (AI) in the educational sector must be investigated and assessed. For example, the indiscriminate introduction of AI could impede student autonomy by providing ready-made and predetermined solutions, thereby diminishing their ability to think and articulate their views independently (UNESCO, 2023). Additionally, this reduces human interaction and endangers the teacher-student relationship, potentially distorting the traditional concept of teaching (UNESCO, 2023).

■ 2. Educational-personal data and Artificial Intelligence (AI)

A significant challenge encountered in the applications of Artificial Intelligence (AI) in education relates to educational-personal data, which serve as the "driving force" behind AI. AI applications are fueled by data, which may have been previously collected or gathered specifically for this purpose. Data collection can occur through existing databases, as well as through sensors, audiovisual recording systems, and other multimodal tools. Subsequently, the data is appropriately processed, and the applications respond based on the specific elements and the predefined function. AI applications have the capability to adapt the data they generate by analyzing past events, doing so with a degree of autonomy and without any intermediate human intervention (Goutziamani, 2024).

The challenges arising from the applications of Artificial Intelligence (AI) in education include, among others, the collection, storage, processing, and securing of educational-personal data, encompassing the privacy and rights of students. The data collection process must adhere to the principles of data minimization and specific purpose. Educational institutions are obligated to clearly define the reasons for collecting educational-personal data and ensure that it is used solely for the intended purpose. Data must be stored in secure environments with stringent measures,

and its processing must comply with legal regulations and the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR). Additionally, educational bodies must be aware of the legal obligations involved in managing educational-personal data and ensure that their practices align with the ethical principles of transparency and fairness.

As Artificial Intelligence (AI) applications evolve, they may even be capable of reading a student's facial expressions, which could reveal a lack of understanding of a topic and modify the lesson accordingly to meet the specific student's needs (Pliakos, 2024). However, real-time recognition of facial expressions requires the student's consent and raises issues of data ownership. The concept of data ownership inherently involves transparency and fairness (Remian, 2019), concerning who holds and who has the right to access personal-educational data. Consent for data collection is often given, but its use may infringe on students' privacy. Ownership might need to be granted to the students themselves, as they are the providers of the data and thereby have the right to control how it is used for their own learning benefit (Holmes et al., 2021). Of course, there is also a reasonable counterargument regarding the rights of educational institutions to use student data, as interactions are recorded within a structured system provided through them (Nguyen et al., 2023).

Under no circumstances should students be transformed into data sources for extracting valuable information. The data collected must be used to improve education and not as marketing commodities. Educational institutions should not use the databases they hold for promotional activities with potential personal gain. Moreover, the European Union enacted GDPR rules in 2016, which have been operational since early 2018, to protect against arbitrary collection, analysis, management, and sharing of personal data. Exceptionally high financial and disciplinary penalties have been established, making it impossible to deceive citizens. However, the question of the capability to conduct the necessary checks remains unanswered (Vergopoulos, 2020).

The principle of data minimization under the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) is crucial when linking personal data with the applications of Artificial Intelligence (AI) in education. This principle dictates that data must be adequate, relevant, and limited to what is necessary for the purposes for which they are processed. However, the more data input into AI applications, the more precise and extensive the outcomes produced. The challenge, then, is how to reconcile the principle of data minimization with the effective functioning of AI applications. One possible solution is the use of anonymization or pseudonymization techniques, which make it difficult or impossible to identify the participants. These techniques allow for the retention of non-identifiable data over extended periods and satisfy operational needs, as well as the principle of limiting the storage period. This approach helps balance the need for comprehensive data to fuel AI functionalities while adhering to GDPR requirements to protect individuals' privacy (Goutziamani, 2024).

What would happen, however, if the principles stipulated by the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) were applied, and the data inputs to Artificial Intelligence (AI) applications in education were limited? Could they function equally effectively, or would applying the principle of data minimization weaken these applications and even lead to erroneous outcomes, since AI "learns" from the data it processes? If AI applications are "trained" on limited data, which do not reflect the entirety of educational-personal data but only a portion, then the generated responses would be correspondingly aligned. This situation raises legitimate concerns, as it presents a conflict with the principle of fair processing, given that AI applications require personal-educational data for smooth operation and to avoid biased outcomes (Goutziamani, 2024). If the provision of necessary data is restricted, the question arises whether it could hinder the progression of science. Could we imagine the situation our society and culture would be in, for example, if Copernicus in 1543, instead of formulating his theory of the heliocentric system, had remained silent? (Pelegriinis, 2009)

■ 3. Protection of educational-personal data

The use of Artificial Intelligence (AI) applications in education frequently results in the generation of substantial data volumes, encompassing sensitive information such as students' personal details, race, ethnicity, gender, performance, emotional and social aspects, preferences, cognitive ability analyses, and other data related to personal and individual development. More specifically, secondary and tertiary educational institutions collect and maintain as part of their services:

Everything related to the academic life of students, such as applications, letters of recommendation, grades, and disciplinary records.

Detailed financial information for both students and their parents, including financial aid applications, income tax returns, employment histories, salaries, loans, work schedules, scholarships, and insurance claims.

Health information gathered by university health centers, university clinics, and university athletic programs about students, faculty, other staff, and their families.

Financial and other personal information regarding employee salaries, insurance coverage, benefits, retirement, travel reimbursements, and vehicle use.

Electronic addresses, sent and received correspondence of students, faculty, and other staff.

Video recording and archiving information from security cameras installed in libraries, parking areas, administrative buildings, school-university stores, financial services, athletic facilities, and hundreds of other locations within the school-university premises.

Titles of all books and articles that are borrowed, accessed often through electronic reservations, purchased from university bookstores, or paid for with credit cards.

Detailed financial and other data about students, alumni, and their potential donations to the university, including assets, salaries, past donations.

Data about vehicles that have access to and park on school-university premises, even temporarily.

Data accessed from external sources for background checks [e.g., educational organizations increasingly use sources like Facebook to monitor their students' online activities] (Aggelidou, 2010).

The aggregation of the aforementioned data raises concerns regarding the potential for interception or improper leakage. Recently publicized cases, which have heightened related concerns, include:

1. The College Board, a non-profit organization that administers entrance exams for attendance at American educational institutions, was fined \$750,000 as it was found to be collecting students' personal data, which it subsequently either sold on the market for profit-making purposes or used for its own promotional activities. According to information released to the public, this organization encouraged students to provide personal information during registration, including their average grades, religious beliefs, and family income. While the collection of this data was optional and legal within the context of connecting candidates with educational institutions and scholarship providers, its improper use during the period 2018-2022 led to the sale of personal data of students from New York to more than 1,000 educational institutions and entities, affecting over 237,000 students in just one year (College Board, 2023).
2. The Los Angeles Unified School District (LAUSD) announced last June that sensitive educational data stored on the well-known management platform Snowflake had been breached. It was revealed that intruders (hackers) had stolen files containing sensitive personal data of students, such as names, social security numbers, and academic performances. The Los Angeles Unified School District (LAUSD) informed the affected parties and collaborated with cybersecurity experts to strengthen their protective measures (Merod, 2023).
3. Educational data purportedly originating from the U.S. Department of Education appeared for sale on the dark web. The origin of these data could not be verified, thus creating doubts about how they were stolen. The sellers claimed to have a total of 27 million records from the database of the U.S. Department of Education. They even published a blurred screenshot with

the caption: "An entire database belonging to the U.S. Department of Education is currently for sale" (US Department of Education Data, 2023).

While the cases mentioned are not directly linked to the applications of Artificial Intelligence (AI) in education, they raise legitimate concerns given the large volume of data generated through these applications. The concerns center around: 1. unfair use or sale of the data, 2. data breaches and public disclosure, and 3. data theft and sale. The concern intensifies as there has been an increase in attacks on educational institutions by malicious software, which attempts to disrupt access to educational data and demands ransom to prevent its publication. Last year, ransomware attacks increased by 92% in K-12 schools and 70% in higher educational institutions. Behind these attacks, primarily targeting educational institutions in the United States and the United Kingdom, appeared well-known ransomware groups such as LockBit and Rhysida (Rapid Increase in Ransomware Attacks, 2023).

The management of educational-personal data is often guided by inconsistent and inadequate policies. Educational institutions—often negligently—pay little attention to privacy and security issues, even though it is estimated that over one-third of data breaches occur within these environments. This lack of focus on data protection exposes schools and universities to significant risks, emphasizing the need for stronger, more consistent security measures and policies to safeguard sensitive information (Aggelidou, 2010).

It should be noted that there have been instances of fake advertisements claiming to sell educational-personal data. This tactic is either used to demonstrate to educational institutions that the perpetrators possess students' personal data and to demand ransom or to find willing buyers and deceive them. Conversely, if the advertisement is genuine, failed negotiations between intruders (hackers) and educational institutions can lead to the leakage of these data on the dark web. This highlights the complex challenges faced by educational institutions in managing security threats and underscores the importance of robust cybersecurity measures and proactive communication strategies to mitigate such risks (US Department of Education Data, 2023).

Amidst the prevailing climate, actions are being taken by governments and educational organizations to bolster cybersecurity. Schools and universities are investing in security systems and training their staff to effectively deal with such threats. Indeed, protecting data and avoiding ransom demands are of paramount importance for their smooth operation (Rapid Increase in Ransomware Attacks, 2023). In the context of securing educational-personal data, it is crucial to keep Artificial Intelligence (AI) applications updated. These applications, like any software, are vulnerable to attacks from malicious software and intruders (hackers). Application developers frequently discover new threats and vulnerabilities in their software, and

updates typically include fixes for these weaknesses. By installing these updates, personal-educational data is protected, and it ensures that sensitive information remains secure (Why We Should Keep Our Applications Updated, 2023).

In every case of unfair use of educational-personal data, we face:

The risk of categorization: Individuals may be categorized based on schematic classification and ranking of their data (especially when the processing involves sensitive personal data), which leads to easier control, discrimination against them, and ultimately manipulation.

The risk of creating a "biographical portrait": The interconnection of information that makes an individual's personality transparent and thus manipulable.

The risk of distorting an individual's image: Exploitation based on potentially negative data, which can perpetuate and even be utilized electronically indefinitely.

The risk of commodification of personal data: Neutralization of privacy, and the transformation of private life into a subject of economic transactions.

These risks underline the crucial importance of ethical management, robust data protection policies, and the implementation of strict regulatory measures to safeguard the rights and privacy of individuals within educational settings (Aggelidou, 2010).

■ 4. Conclusions

In conclusion, Artificial Intelligence (AI) applications in education do not replace the traditional teacher-student relationship, but rather serve as a valuable aid in the educational process. However, the generation of large volumes of data creates concerns about the violation of rights and privacy of all involved parties (students and educators) and raises questions about their protection, storage, and potential misuse. This situation gives the impression that those involved are exposed to unknown and potentially harmful risks. Therefore, it's essential to balance the benefits of AI in education with rigorous safeguards to protect personal data and uphold the integrity of educational environments.

The educational community must acknowledge the seriousness of cybersecurity and invest in modern protection systems. Systematic training in cybersecurity and the implementation of advanced data protection technologies are crucial to prevent future data breaches. The challenges of the digital age must be addressed proactively, as, combined with the human-centered nature of Artificial Intelligence (AI) applications (Educational Community, 2023), they reinforce the need for human oversight, making educational institutions consistently accountable for any "mistakes." After all, AI itself cannot be held accountable, and the human creator must always be solely responsible (Nguyen, 2023). Moreover, higher educational institu-

tions must lead the national dialogue on the proper protection of educational-personal data. The university community must assume its responsibilities, given the progressively increasing demand for educational-personal data, the unique nature of its mission, and its relationships with students and all involved parties. This leadership role is essential not only in implementing security measures but also in shaping the policies and ethical standards governing AI and data use within educational environments (Nguyen, 2023).

To build a relationship of trust in the use of Artificial Intelligence (AI) in education and to alleviate related concerns, it is essential to ensure that personal-educational data are safeguarded and cannot be intercepted or accessed by third parties in any way. It is of vital importance to guarantee their security through the application of all relevant protocols and regulations. Only in this way will it become evident that this technological achievement does not pose a threat to those involved but serves as a valuable learning tool.

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